

USING INNOVATIVE PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES TO TEACH STUDENTS THE CONCEPT OF WEB DESIGN IN THE IT AND INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY CLASS

Kuldasheva Feruza Kurdoshevna

Teacher of AL at TDIU

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Abstract. *In this article, in the process of explaining the concept of Web-design to students of the academic lyceum, it is envisaged to organize classes based on the global requirements, based on the personal abilities of each student. The teacher should perform the role of a manager in developing the creative ability, new ideas, not thinking in a single mold, originality, and initiative of students studying in academic lyceums. For this purpose, the correct and efficient use of modern pedagogical technologies, various games, methods and methods in the course of teacher training will have a good effect.*

Keywords: *web design, creativity, traditional, creativity, brainstorming, Venn diagram, success.*

Currently, the selection of talented students in academic lyceums according to their chosen fields is a requirement of the times. In order to further develop students' knowledge and skills in the course of the lesson, each training session should be organized at a high level in order to enter the higher education institution of their choice in the future. The teacher's level of knowledge and pedagogical skills play a big role in this. When organizing lessons, each teacher must not leave out any student and pay great attention to the topic of the lesson. In fact, information technology science, which is rapidly developing now, occupies an important place in the life of students, as every science has its own.

If we look at our history, we can see that the science of pedagogy has appeared in our country since ancient times. This is evidenced by the following thoughts of the great scholar Ibn Sina: "A teacher should be restrained when dealing with children. He should pay special attention to how the students implement the knowledge they have acquired. In the educational process, it is necessary to use different methods and forms of working with students, take into account their individual characteristics and make them interested in lessons. The teacher's thoughts should be open to all students. He should accompany his words with facial expressions and gestures, so that the lesson becomes more understandable and evokes an emotional reaction in children" [1].

This approach must be considered by every teacher. Each subject teacher will achieve his/her goal if he/she uses modern pedagogical technologies based on his/her subject. In the teaching of informatics and information technology, the teacher requires the use of methodology, paying attention to each of its directions.

In the course of the lesson, it is appropriate for the teacher to use problem-based learning, which forms the skills and abilities of students, such as creative research, conducting small research, putting forward certain hypotheses, justifying the results, and coming to certain conclusions. .

The main goal of problem-based learning is to help students fully understand the problem and teach them to solve it. One of the main examples of problem-based education in practice is to

create a problem situation related to the studied topic. Teachers of various academic subjects should anticipate the creation of problem situations and ways of solving them in the course of the lesson.

When explaining the topic of Informatics and Information Technology, "Understanding Web Design" to students, using "Brainstorming", "Venn Diagram" technologies, and "My Test" or online test programs, students can read the above topic quickly and easily. they will

In the process of transitioning to a web design topic, you can use Brainstorming technology as follows:

Question 1	What does the word web mean?	Web- "net" means the Internet network
Question 2	What is design?	Design (: design - "project", "drawing", "picture") - a term representing the types of design activities aimed at the formation of the aesthetic and functional qualities of the environment of objects
Question 3	What is web design?	Web design (web design from English) type of designing web user interfaces for web sites, web applications
Question 4	What is a web page?	Web page is a hypertext document on the WWW
Question 5	What is a website?	Web- net, site- place means a set of electronic documents located at one electronic address in the computer network.
Question 6	Who is a web designer and what does he create?	Web designers: designing the logical structure of web pages; who comes up with the most convenient solutions for presenting information; is involved in the design of the web project.
Question 7	What programs are used to create web design?	Photo shop, Corel draw, HTML, CSS, Java Script,...

After the concept of web design is explained to the students, it is appropriate to use the Venn diagram in the comparative study of the programs used in it.

This is a form of organizing teaching through graphic images in pedagogical technology, which is represented by the image of two intersecting circles. These foundations allow to consider the analysis and synthesis of ideas from two aspects, to identify their common and differentiating aspects, and to compare them. Students are combined into pairs of two people and suggest to them the specific, different aspects (or the opposite) of the concept or basis under consideration by writing them in circles; at the next stage, the participants are divided into small groups of four, and each pair introduces its analysis to the group members;

after listening to the analysis of the pairs, they get together, find the common aspects or differences of the considered problem or concepts, summarize and write in the intersecting part of the circles.

As an example, the task of using Photoshop and HTML in web design can be analyzed in a Venn diagram as follows.

A-Photoshop, B-HTML

<p>B A</p> <p>When creating pictures for magazines;</p> <p>When processing</p>	<p>When decorating web pages;</p> <p>When creating web pages; When creating e-books;</p>	<p>and use them together in</p>
<p>In this practice.</p>	<p>It</p>	<p>par</p>

At the end of the lesson, questions are asked in the programs "My test" and "Online tests" to strengthen the knowledge and skills of the students.

In conclusion, it can be said that with the help of the above mentioned methods, students will have the ability to apply the knowledge gained during the lesson in practice.

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